

Emerging Country CEOs' Cognitively Deep State and Environmentalism: Experiment Setting in Precariat Behaviours to Finance ESG (Environmental, Social and Governance) Investments

ABSTRACT

This study investigates whether CEOs occupying top positions in emerging countries have a responsibility to allocate ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) investments, taking into account their cognitively deep state and environmentalism. It deepens our understanding of CEOs' behaviours, driven by ecosystem characteristics, and how they are likely to uphold genuine moralities and environmental missions. It employs an experimental setting to examine CEOs' precariat characteristics when they should spend the firms' funds to invest in ESG programs without receiving bonuses or compensation. It measures CEOs' cognitive deep state and environmentalism, which affect their bonding motivations toward financing ESG investments. Contradictorily, they may shirk disbursing funds for ESG investments, such as precariat behaviours. This study finds that emerging country CEOs exhibit high levels of cognitively deep state and environmentalism, which profoundly affect their willingness to finance ESG investments. Moreover, despite CEOs not receiving bonuses or compensation, they spend the firm's funds on ESG programs. They undertake ESG programs as unremunerated activities, thereby reducing their material welfare. Finally, this study finds that kinetic-active learning for the cognitively deep state and environmentalism can eliminate precariat beliefs and behaviours. It argues that CEOs' mindsets in the cognitively deep state and environmentalism are primary determinants of their willingness to finance ESG investments. It also demonstrates that emerging country CEOs with deep-state and environmentalist mindsets discard precariat behaviours without considering the bonuses and compensation they will receive. Thus, most CEOs in emerging countries have low precariatism, advancing ESGs' mission with high multidimensional commitment.

Keywords: Cognitively Deep State; Environmentalism; Precariat; Behaviour; Finance; ESG;

1. INTRODUCTION

This study investigates CEOs' behaviours in emerging countries when deciding whether to invest the firm's funds in ESG (Environmental, Social and Governance) expenditures. Moreover, it deepens CEOs' precariat behaviours because financing ESG programs can likely reduce their bonuses and compensation, unrecognised measured performance, or other budgeted activities (Ben Ali & Chouaibi, 2023; S. Cohen et al., 2023; Keddie & Magnan, 2023). Furthermore, it argues that CEOs' cognitive depth and environmentalism can help them discard their precariat behaviours (Kaplan, 2008; Liu et al., 2024; L. Zhang et al., 2020). Thus, they still finance ESG investments, despite their reduced material welfare, supported by their mental health regarding the deep state and environmentalism. In other words, this study analyses the substance of CEOs' deep state and environmentalism in relation to their precariat behaviours, and vice versa. Then, it reveals that the CEOs view ESG investments as a form of knowledge supremacy (Back et al., 2020; Dabbebi et al., 2022; Eccles et al., 2020) whenever the deep state and environmentalism are seen as superior to the precariat. However, it notes that ESG investments will reduce CEOs' material welfare, such as bonuses and compensation, and will not recognise their performance.

This study comprehends some extant research concentrating on ESG investments relating to CEOs' narcissism (Back et al., 2020; Dabbebi et al., 2022; Martínez-Ferrero et al., 2024), earning management (Kontesa et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2023; L. Zhang et al., 2020), social identification and corporate irresponsibility (Gao et al., 2023; Lassoued & Khanchel, 2023; Riera & Iborra, 2023), and unethical corporate behaviours (Ben Ali & Chouaibi, 2023; Hou et al., 2024; Keddie & Magnan, 2023). It identifies research gaps regarding CEOs' behaviours in the deep state and environmentalism, with a focus on mental health. They recognise environmental problems arising from the firm's explorations and excavations, which need to be addressed, though they will have to spend funds to repair the damage. Furthermore, this study encompasses extant research on ESG investments conducted by irresponsible CEOs (Gao et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2024; L. Zhang et al., 2020). It reveals why CEOs discard their precariat behaviours (Kaplan, 2008;

Lassoued & Khanchel, 2023; Liu et al., 2024), maintaining their countries' sustainable environments. By this means, emerging country CEOs abandon their precariat mentality and substance in favour of their deep state and environmentalism for ESG investments.

This study raises its freshness in three arguments. First, it explains that emerging-country CEOs are concerned about ESG investments, particularly spending on environmental sustainability. Mental healthiness in the cognitively deep state (Mahran & Elamer, 2024; Venugopal et al., 2023; L. Zhang et al., 2020) and environmentalism (Kaplan, 2008; Liu et al., 2024; L. Zhang et al., 2020) support emerging country CEOs' beliefs, attitudes and behaviours to maintain and improve environmental sustainability (Abatecola & Cristofaro, 2019; Chege & Wang, 2020; Naciti, 2019). Emerging country CEOs have individual political leadership to secure environments through their motivations to finance ESG investments. Thus, these CEOs align with their state's mission and goals for sustainable environments (Dabbebi et al., 2022; Eccles et al., 2020; Li et al., 2024) in which they live and work. Their mental health, as environmentalists do, is also advancing CEOs' ideology in social ecology. Thus, CEOs exhibit cognitions and affections to practically balance the relationship between humans and natural systems (Mahran & Elamer, 2024; Mirza et al., 2024; Ren et al., 2022) to construct sustainability.

Second, this study reveals that emerging country CEOs are advancing their substance of the deep state and environmentalism over precariat behaviours for ESG investments. The CEOs' behavioural substances innovate their environmental leadership (Eccles et al., 2020; J. Li et al., 2024; Mahran & Elamer, 2024) and the balance of the relationship between human and nature systems (Mirza et al., 2024; Ren et al., 2022; Velte, 2019). Although they will incur reduced material welfare due to spending on ESG investments, they choose to finance all typical activities related to ESG programs. They choose to allocate the firm's funds to ESG programs by reducing their material and psychological well-being (Back et al., 2020; S. Cohen et al., 2023; Gärling & Jansson, 2021). This study argues that they know the environmental sustainability they should maintain and preserve (Chege & Wang, 2020; G. Cohen, 2023; Naciti, 2019). They prioritise ESG investments as a matter of political supremacy to fulfil the Paris Agreement. They undertake and implement the mandates of the Paris Agreement, acting as emerging-country agencies with entrenched executive careers.

Third, this study reveals the CEOs' behavioural bonding to ESG investments in emerging countries through experimental settings. Meanwhile, most extant research has not employed a methodological approach grounded in empirical quantitative methods. This study focuses on an experimental setting, seeking internal consistency (Gyönyörövá et al., 2023; Khemir et al., 2019; Utz, 2019) and validity of conclusions (Ben Ali & Chouaibi, 2023; Chege & Wang, 2020; Mahran & Elamer, 2024). Furthermore, it identifies and analyses emerging country CEOs' behaviours in conducting ESG investments, whether they are pervasive or entrenched characteristics (Gao et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2024; L. Zhang et al., 2020). Thus, CEOs engaging in ESG investment practices in emerging countries are not performing because they do not feel like it. By this means, emerging country CEOs make serious ESG investments to maintain and protect human and natural systems and make them more sustainable, which benefits future generations.

First, this study contributes to the literature by showing that emerging country CEOs prioritise political supremacy when making ESG investments. Moreover, it explains that CEOs' behaviours regarding mental health and the deep state, and their support for environmentalism, support this supreme placement (Back et al., 2020; Dabbebi et al., 2022; Eccles et al., 2020). They show their political leadership in ESG programs, spending the firm's funds that probably reduce their material welfare. Moreover, they demonstrate the need to balance the relationship between humans and natural systems to ensure consistent sustainability. From the relational agency perspective, emerging country CEOs are bound by United Nations mandates to implement the ESG agenda, as reflected in international jurisprudence (Gao et al., 2023; Hoang et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023). Thus, this study demonstrates that emerging country CEOs face low moral hazard to shirk the United Nations' ESG mandates (Orzes et al., 2020; Riera & Iborra, 2023; Xu et al., 2024), as evidenced in their entrenched beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours.

The second contribution is the elimination of precariat behaviours for all people facing the prospective ESG, primarily environmental issues. Moreover, this study argues that precariat behavioural eliminations depend on ESG knowledge that should further be disseminated to societies (Ben Ali & Chouaibi, 2023; Hoang et al., 2023; X. Zhang et al., 2020). Then it explains the need for knowledge domains that foster collective cognition in societies. These knowledge domains are that ESG investments do not reduce material and psychological welfare. However, ESG investments yield long-run increases in material and psychological welfare that future generations will enjoy (Badia et al., 2022; Consolandi et al.,

2020, 2022). The second knowledge domain is the need for principled moralities to discard the precariat or proletariat mentality (Back et al., 2020; Orzes et al., 2020; Y. Xu et al., 2024) when people face ESG problems. At least, all these knowledge domains should help people understand the moral basis for charity to nature as an equivalent to alms for people experiencing poverty.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUNDS AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Political Supremacy of Cognitively Deep State and Environmentalism

This study identified extant research on CEOs' irresponsibility in ESG implementation (Gao et al., 2023; Lassoued & Khanchel, 2023; Riera & Iborra, 2023) and ESG misconduct (Martínez-Ferrero et al., 2024; Menla Ali et al., 2024; Mirza et al., 2024). Then it criticises these phenomena, carried out by people who lack knowledge of ESG implementation, which are likely to have no future beneficial effects. Moreover, regulators, such as state or national governments, did not prioritise ESG implementation at the highest level of political authority. Meanwhile, this study argues that CEOs' irresponsibility in ESG programs and ESG misconduct are absent when the regulator emphasises the need for people's cognitive deep state and environmentalism to achieve political supremacy (Back et al., 2020; Dabbebi et al., 2022; Eccles et al., 2020). Consequently, people and CEOs hold the cognitively deep state and environmentalism as pervasive memories in their beliefs and behaviours, which can be further actualised. Thus, placing the cognitively deep state and environmentalism at the state's political supremacy is beneficial, and the remaining activities are to treat it as collective social cognition.

Furthermore, this study argues the need for genuine inducements of the cognitively deep state and environmentalism into CEOs' and people's cognitions. It argues that ESG implementation requires organisational and pragmatic leadership, grounded in the deep state, to establish efficient practices (Badía et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2023; Parameswar et al., 2023). These ESG implementations include strategic expansions for practical, widespread use, such as evacuations from negative directions (Consolandi et al., 2020, 2022; Ronalter et al., 2023). Simultaneously, environmentalism proposes a strategic agenda to balance the relationship between humans and natural systems (Mahran & Elamer, 2024; Ren et al., 2022; Velte, 2019). The strategic agenda requires definitive controls, evaluations, and measurements for ESG implementations because its planned agenda relates to human moral hazards and opportunistic behaviours (Fiaschi et al., 2020; Riera & Iborra, 2023; X. Zhang et al., 2020). Finally, this study reveals that when ESG investments are delayed or cancelled due to political interference, the likely future costs of repairing human and natural damage will increase.

2.2. Discarding Precariat Behaviours

Precariat beliefs and behaviours affect successive ESG investments because material and psychological welfare are primary decision-making keys. People and CEOs who experience precariousness tend to avoid unremunerated activities, even though they should do them (Dabbebi et al., 2022; Ren et al., 2022; Velte, 2019). In the context of behavioural responses, CEOs may finance ESG investments even though they are not assigned to do so because they already have additional jobs. ESG investments and implementations are temporary jobs not paid by bonus and compensation systems (Ben Ali & Chouaibi, 2023; G. Cohen, 2023; Keddie & Magnan, 2023). Thus, ESG investments do not affect CEOs' material and psychological welfare (Back et al., 2020; Gärling & Jansson, 2021; Liu et al., 2023). Emerging country CEOs can impactfully align with or shirk the ESG agenda, whether with precarious people. When they become precarious CEOs, they will gratify ESG investments and implementations (Badía et al., 2022; Fiaschi et al., 2020; Parameswar et al., 2023). From a hegemonic perspective, those CEOs engage in performativity, presenting ESG investments as camouflage and as exemplary accomplishments.

From a successive perspective, this study argues that ESG investments will perform well when precariat beliefs and behaviours are discarded. Moreover, it raises the idea that CEOs' cognitively deep state and environmentalism can eliminate these precariousities (Ben Ali & Chouaibi, 2023; Hoang et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023). It reveals that the deep state and environmentalism defeat precarious beliefs and behaviours by failing to consider material welfare. Conversely, CEOs' cognitively deep state and environmentalism choose forward-looking orientations that focus on humans, nature and the relationships between human and natural systems (Back et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2024; Mahran & Elamer, 2024). Finally, the authors demonstrate that mental health in the cognitively deep state and environmentalism are needed to overcome CEOs' adverse selection, intellectual opportunism, and performativity (Fiaschi et al., 2020; Wright, 2023; X. Zhang et al., 2020) in the conduct of ESG programs. Hence, without precariat beliefs and

behaviours, CEOs can sustainably manage ESG investments and initiatives by recognising the humanities as ESG participants.

2.3. Hypotheses Development

This study argues that emerging country CEOs' deep state has capacities in the state's political leadership. Consequently, they can lead and control ESG investments because of their entrenched executive careers. When they receive ESG investment mandates, they act and behave in line with the state's mission and goals (Eccles et al., 2020; Riera & Iborra, 2023; Young, 1991). They fulfil the Paris Agreement and ESG mandates for the CEOs to state where they live and work, leading to successful ESG investments. In other words, they bond these mandates, determining their low precariat behaviours. They are still making an effort to make successful ESG investments. This study then formulates hypothesis H1 below.

H1: CEOs with high cognitively deep states conduct lower precariat behavioural decision-making (**H1.a**) and have higher bonding (**H1.b**) to finance ESG investments and implementations than those with low.

The authors argue that the environmentalism of emerging country CEOs is oriented toward creating sustainable humans, nature, and the relationship between humans and natural systems (Back et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2023; Ren et al., 2022). From an ethical perspective, this study explains that these CEOs maintain the environment to ensure it remains sustainable. Environmentalists are forward-looking, considering the consequences of their actions on nature and its resources for future generations (Consolandi et al., 2020, 2022; Utz, 2019). Ethics and orientations shape CEOs, not precariat beliefs and behaviours. Then, these CEOs are motivated to maintain ESG investments, including financing policy. Therefore, this study proposes the following hypothesis (H2).

H2: CEOs with high levels of environmentalism exhibit lower precariat behaviours (**H2.a**) and higher genuine conduct (**H2.b**) in holding ESG investments and implementations than those with low levels.

Combining hypotheses H1 and H2, this study argues that cognitively deep states and environmentalism defeat precarious beliefs and behaviours. The CEOs' deep state and environmentalism do not share many of the characteristics of precariousness. They focus on sustainable ESG, especially in green environments (Dabbebi et al., 2022; Dmuchowski et al., 2023; Eccles et al., 2020). Moreover, they defeat their behaviourally adverse selections for the ESG programs, elevating ESG to the highest political prominence, including its knowledge. Consequently, they do not deliberately take remuneration for ESG activities because they prioritise ESG substance over the material and psychological benefits they will receive. Therefore, this study develops the following hypothesis (H3).

H3: CEOs with high cognitive depth and high environmentalism engage in lower precariat behavioural decision-making (H3.a) and have higher bonding (H3.b) to finance ESG investments and implementation than those with low cognitive depth and low environmentalism.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

3.1. Measurements, Experimental Designs and Participants

This research uses measurements of variables related to the deep state (Fiaschi et al., 2020; Parameswar et al., 2023; Wright, 2023) and environmentalism (Abatecola & Cristofaro, 2019; Dmuchowski et al., 2023; Orzes et al., 2020). It notes that the deep-state variable is transformed into a cognitively deep-state variable, becoming an individual-unit analysis. When measuring participants' cognitive depth and environmentalism, it uses the bilingual languages of English and Indonesian to preserve face validity and content validity. **Appendix A** presents two variables measuring cognitively deep states and environmentalism. Furthermore, this study designs its experimental setting to elicit precariat behaviours (Gyönyörövá et al., 2023; Khemir et al., 2019; Utz, 2019), which are then presented to participants. It records participants' decision-making on financing ESG investments. Then, it values participants not having to decide on financing, thereby decreasing financing requirements and increasing the level of financed ESG investments. Not having to decide whether to finance ESG investments is valued as the highest level of precariat behaviour. The activity flow of measurements and treatments is programmed at

<https://esgprecarity.org> and is open to the public. **Appendix B** presents this study’s protocol for the experiment. **Figure 1** presents the flow of data collection, measurement, and treatment activities.

This study selects participants through a purposive sampling method. The designed criteria are (1) all typical CEOs of finance, marketing, operation-production, and others; (2) having work experience of more than five years; and (3) selected industries of manufacturing, mining, forestry, and agriculture. The authors argue that these criteria meet firms’ obligations to pay ESG expenses, such as carbon dioxide compensation. Finally, this study explains that each participant should follow the experimental protocol, as summarised in the activity flow in Figure 1. First, it collects general information about participants’ works and others. Second, it measures participants’ high-low cognitive depth and environmentalism. Third, it treats participants’ precariat beliefs and behaviours. It presents multiple cases that participants should solve to finance ESG investments and hold ESG. Fourth, it values participants’ answers in their precariat scores, which they optionally finance and hold, as well as in ESG investments and implementations. Simultaneously, this protocol experiment produces a data structure, as shown in Table 1 below. **Finally, this study received ethical approval from the Health Research Ethics Committee, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Negeri Semarang, under approval number 815/KEPK/FK/KLE/2025. All research procedures were conducted in accordance with established ethical guidelines and relevant regulations. Participation in this study was entirely voluntary, and participants were explicitly informed of their right to refuse to participate or withdraw from the study at any stage, without consequences. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before data collection. To ensure confidentiality and anonymity, all participant data were anonymised and used solely for research purposes.**

Figure 1 Activity Flow

Table 1 Data Structure

		Environmentalism		Environmentalism	
		High	Low	High	Low
Cognitively	High	Cell-A	Cell-B	Cell-A'	Cell-B'
Deep State	Low	Cell-D	Cell-C	Cell-D'	Cell-C'
		Before		After	

3.2. Reliability, Validity and Statistical Tests

This study conducts reliability and validity tests for the measured variables. It uses confirmatory factor analysis to ascertain convergent and discriminant validity. It also states that, before the questionnaires are disseminated to participants, they are tested for content and face validity, even though bilingualists are employed. After collecting the data, this research compares the mean values to evidence for the examination. Thus, it uses parametric tests, such as independent-samples t-tests, and can switch to nonparametric tests when the data are not normally distributed.

4. STATISTICAL RESULTS

4.1. Statistical Descriptive

Table 2 presents the demographic characteristics of the 588 research participants. The information presented includes participants’ gender, age group, education level, and occupation. Based on gender composition, participants were relatively evenly split, with 57% male and 43% female, indicating no gender dominance. Moreover, by age group, Gen Z and Millennials are the largest group. This condition reflects

the growing proportion of workers in this age range in the current workforce. In addition, companies tend to recruit more individuals from this generation because they are considered more adaptable to change and more concerned about sustainability issues. In terms of education level, the distribution of participants also shows a relatively balanced composition, with 120 (20%) holding a diploma degree, 191 (32%) holding a bachelor's degree, 166 (29%) holding a master's degree, and 111 (19%) holding a doctorate (PhD). Meanwhile, by occupation, the majority of participants worked as accountants (69%), while the remaining 31% were auditors and lecturers.

Table 2 Participants' Demography

Respondents Data	Numbers	Percentage
Gender:		
Male	335	57%
Female	253	43%
Age:		
19-26	143	23%
27-40	275	47%
41-50	170	30%
Education level:		
Diploma Degree	120	20%
Bachelor Degree	191	32%
Master Degree	166	29%
PhD Degree	111	19%
Jobs:		
Accountant	168	29%
Staff Accounting	237	40%
Auditor	87	15%
Lecturer	96	16%

Table 3 presents descriptive statistics for the two main variables analysed in this study: cognitively deep state and environmentalism. Panel A shows the distribution characteristics of these two variables through mean values and data dispersion. The mean value for the cognitively deep state was 3.227, while the mean value for environmentalism was 1.272. These mean values show that the two variables are at different levels but have relatively comparable distribution patterns. The mean values are then used as a cut-off point to group participants into high- and low-category groups. This categorisation approach provides a more structured analysis of references to participant characteristics based on their cognitively deep state.

Table 3 Descriptive Statistics

Panel A: Measured Variables

Variable	Min.	Max.	Mean	Modus	Median	Std. Dev
Cognitively Deep State	1	5	3.227	5	3.857	1.272
Environmentalism	1	5	2.911	2	2.250	1.259

Panel B: Data Structure

		Environmentalism		Environmentalism	
		High	Low	High	Low
Cognitively Deep State	High	Cell-A n: 145 \bar{x} : 73.431 Std.Dev.: 21.782	Cell-B n: 144 \bar{x} : 63.403 Std.Dev.: 26.366	Cell-A' n: 145 \bar{x} : 91.545 Std.Dev.: 14.430	Cell-B' n: 144 \bar{x} : 79.285 Std.Dev.: 16.636
	Low	Cell-D n: 149 \bar{x} : 65.034 Std.Dev.: 14.196	Cell-C n: 150 \bar{x} : 61.583 Std.Dev.: 19.790	Cell-D' n: 149 \bar{x} : 85.342 Std.Dev.: 14.951	Cell-C' n: 150 \bar{x} : 62 Std.Dev.: 19.790
		Before		After	

Treatment:
Precariat Beliefs & Behaviours

Table 3, Panel B, presents descriptive statistics for each combination of cognitively deep state and environmentalism categories, including the number of participants, mean values, and standard deviations for each cell. In general, the number of participants per cell is relatively balanced, averaging 147 respondents per cell. The highest number of participants was in cell C, namely 150 participants in the low cognitive depth and low environmentalism categories, with a mean of 61.583 and a standard deviation of 19.790. After being given treatment in the form of precariat beliefs and behaviours, cell C' showed a mean value of 62 with a standard deviation of 19.790. Conversely, the lowest number of participants was in cell B, namely 144 participants in the high cognitive depth and low environmentalism categories, with a statistical mean of 63.403 and a standard deviation of 26.366. After the treatment was administered, cell B' experienced an increase in the mean value to 79.285 with a standard deviation of 16.636. Overall, the data pattern shows consistency in the comparison between the cognitively deep state and environmentalism categories, both before and after treatment. Thus, the stability of the data structure indicates that further statistical analysis can be conducted effectively.

4.2. Validity and Reliability Tests

Table 4 shows the results of validity and reliability testing for all measurement items. **Table 4** shows that the variables of cognitively deep state and environmentalism meet the required psychometric criteria. All item correlation values are above the Pearson product-moment critical value ($n= 588$), and all items show factor loading values above 0.700. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values are 0.784 for the cognitively deep state and 0.730 for environmentalism, confirming high convergent validity. Internal consistency was also verified by high Cronbach's alpha values (0.954 and 0.971) and composite reliability values that exceeded the normative threshold of 0.700. In addition, the results of the confirmatory factor analysis indicated that discriminant validity was supported, as each item's factor loading was higher than its construct's AVE (Cheung et al., 2024). These findings are in line with the reliability standards recommended in previous literature (Sumiyana & Sriwidharmanely, 2020), so that both variables are declared valid, reliable, and suitable for further statistical analysis.

Table 4 Validity and Reliability Tests

Variables	Item	Loading Factor	AVE	Corrected-Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha
Cognitively Deep State	CDS1	0.903	0.784	0.864	0.954
	CDS2	0.894		0.853	
	CDS3	0.881		0.835	
	CDS4	0.897		0.857	
	CDS5	0.875		0.828	
	CDS6	0.871		0.824	
	CDS7	0.875		0.828	
Environmentalism	Env1	0.821	0.730	0.791	0.971
	Env2	0.840		0.806	
	Env3	0.859		0.84	
	Env4	0.835		0.819	
	Env5	0.850		0.832	
	Env6	0.883		0.875	
	Env7	0.858		0.848	
	Env8	0.885		0.881	
	Env9	0.873		0.861	
	Env10	0.877		0.866	
	Env11	0.852		0.837	
	Env12	0.841		0.828	

Env13	0.818	0.786
Env14	0.782	0.734

Note: n: 588 participants

4.3. Hypotheses Testing

Table 5 presents a comparison of participants' performance across all experimental cells, by cognitively deep state and environmentalism. This table is divided into two panels: Panel A presents the conditions before treatment, in terms of precariat beliefs and behaviours, and Panel B presents the conditions after treatment. Each hypothesis is explained by the statistical result consistency between before (Panel A) and after (Panel B) treatments, showing robust results with increased mean values. The analysis of both panels aims to test the three research hypotheses using independent sample t-tests. Hypothesis H1.a states that participants as CEOs with a high level of cognitively deep state tend to exhibit lower levels of precariat behaviour in decision-making than CEOs with a low level. The results of the test in Panel A (before treatment) show a significant difference between the two groups, with a mean of 64.014 and a t-value of 3.291 at the 1% significance level. The results of the statistical tests on Panel B (after treatment) also show a consistent pattern with a mean value of 64.014 and a t-value of 3.253, which remains significant at the 1% level. The statistical test results for the before-and-after treatment show that a high level of cognitive depth is systematically associated with lower precariat behaviour in CEO decision-making. Therefore, based on the analysis results in both panels, hypothesis H1.a is consistently supported for both before and after treatment.

On the other hand, hypothesis H1.b states that CEOs with a high level of cognitively deep state have a stronger commitment to financing ESG investments and their implementation than CEOs with a low level of cognitively deep state. The results of the analysis in Panel A represent the conditions before the precariat beliefs and behaviours treatment was administered, showing a significant difference between the two groups, with a statistical mean of 68.434 and a t-value of 2.929 at the 1% significance level. The statistical test results in Panel B, after the treatment, show a stronger increase in the difference, with a mean value of 85.436 and a t-value of 8.018, which is also significant at the 1% level. This increase shows that the treatment strengthens the relationship between the level of cognitively deep state and CEO commitment to ESG financing and implementation. These findings indicate that CEOs with greater cognitive depth exhibit stronger leadership in controlling ESG investment decisions and a greater ability to comply with international mandates and commitments, such as the Paris Agreement. This compliance reflects a long-run orientation and normative responsibility in strategic decision-making (Eccles et al., 2020; Riera & Iborra, 2023; Young, 1991). Thus, overall, the empirical test results provide strong support for hypothesis H1, including sub-hypotheses H1.a and H1.b.

Table 5 Hypotheses Test Results

Panel A: Before Treatment

Hypotheses Comparisons	Mean; Std.Dev.	Mean Diff.	t-value (sign.)	
H1.a: Cell-A,B > Cell-C,D	64.014; 50.671	50.079; 50.080	13.343	3.291***
H1.b: Cell-A,B > Cell-C,D	68.434; 63.304	82.650; 27.291	5.130	2.929***
H2.a: Cell-A,D > Cell-B,C	70.068; 44.558	64.874; 49.788	25.510	6.461***
H2.b: Cell-A,D > Cell-B,C	69.175; 62.476	73.779; 23.224	6.699	3.846***
H3.a: Cell-A > B	78.621; 49.306	50.140; 49.170	29.315	5.433***
H3.a: Cell-A > C	78.621; 40.000	50.140; 49.154	38.621	7.306***
H3.a: Cell-A > B,C	78.621; 44.558	50.140; 49.788	34.063	7.125***
H3.b: Cell-A > B	73.431; 63.403	73.782; 26.366	10.028	3.526***
H3.b: Cell-A > C	73.431; 61.583	73.782; 29.790	11.848	4.893***
H3.b: Cell-A > B,C	73.431; 62.476	73.782; 23.224	10.955	4.743***

Panel B: After Treatment

Hypotheses Comparisons	Mean; Std.Dev.	Mean Diff.	t-value (sign.)	
H1.a: Cell-A',B' > Cell-C',D'	64.014; 50.836	50.079; 50.077	13.178	3.253***
H1.b: Cell-A',B' > Cell-C',D'	85.436; 73.632	82.710; 27.879	11.804	8.018***

H2.a: Cell-A',D' > Cell-B',C'	70.068; 44.558	64.875; 49.788	25.510	6.461***
H2.b: Cell-A',D' > Cell-B',C'	88.401; 70.466	74.997; 23.904	17.935	13.167***
H3.a: Cell-A' > B'	78.621; 49.306	50.140; 49.170	29.315	5.433***
H3.a: Cell-A' > C'	78.621; 40.000	50.140; 49.154	38.621	7.306***
H3.a: Cell-A' > B',C'	78.621; 44.558	50.140; 49.788	34.063	7.125***
H3.b: Cell-A' > B'	91.545; 79.285	74.430; 26.636	12.260	6.694***
H3.b: Cell-A' > C'	91.545; 62.000	74.430; 28.746	29.545	17.386***
H3.b: Cell-A' > B',C'	91.545; 70.536	74.430; 24.895	21.009	12.295***

Noted: Significances at levels: ***(1%); **(5%); *(10%)

Hypothesis H2.a states that CEOs with high levels of environmentalism exhibit lower precariat behaviour and thus adhere more closely to ESG financing and implementation principles than CEOs with low environmentalism. The test results in [Table 5](#), Panel A, show that, both before and after treatment, the difference between the two groups remains significant, with a mean value of 70.068 and a t-value of 6.461 at the 1% significance level. In addition, the standard deviation values before and after treatment were relatively stable at 64.874 and 64.875, respectively. These results indicate consistency in data variation and stability in the treated variable, participants' decision-making to invest in ESG. On the other side, hypothesis H2.b states that CEOs with high levels of environmentalism exhibit greater sincerity in maintaining ESG investments and implementing ESG initiatives than CEOs with low levels of environmentalism. Empirical results in Panel A before treatment show a mean value of 69.175 with a t-value of 3.846. After treatment was administered, the statistical mean increased significantly to 88.401 ($t = 13.167$), which is significant at the 1% level. The consistency of the standard deviation values before and after treatment further strengthens the reliability of the test results. These findings indicate that CEOs with a strong environmentalism orientation tend to consider the ethical consequences and long-run sustainability implications of their decisions on the environment and natural resources for future generations (Consolandi et al., 2020, 2022; Utz, 2019). Thus, the empirical results provide strong support for hypothesis H2, including subhypotheses H2.a and H2.b.

Hypothesis H3.a predicts that CEOs with high levels of cognitively deep state and environmentalism exhibit lower precariat behaviour in financing decisions and ESG implementation than CEOs with low levels of cognitively deep state and environmentalism. The results of the analysis in [Table 5](#), both before (Panel A) and after treatment (Panel B), on precariat beliefs and behaviours, show a consistent pattern. Panel A results 1% significant level. In Panel B, the mean value was 78.621 with a standard deviation of 50.140 and a t-value of 7.125, which is significant at the 1% level. On the other hand, hypothesis H3.b suggests that CEOs with high levels of cognitively deep state and environmentalism have a greater commitment to financing ESG investments and their implementation than CEOs with low levels of cognitively deep state and environmentalism. The statistical results before treatment show a mean value of 73.431, a standard deviation of 73.782, and a t-value of 4.743, which is significant at the 1% level. After treatment, the mean values increased significantly to 91.545 (standard deviation = 74.430), and the t-value increased to 12.295. This increase indicates that the treatment strengthened the relationship between a cognitively deep state and environmentalism, as well as CEO commitment to ESG investment. Overall, these findings show that a combination of high levels of cognitive depth and environmentalism can significantly reduce, and even eliminate, the tendency toward precarious behaviour in CEOs' ESG decision-making (Dabbebi et al., 2022; Dmuchowski et al., 2023; Eccles et al., 2020). The treatment cases of precariatism strengthen CEOs' concerns and long-run orientations toward sustainable ESG investment. Thus, the empirical results provide strong support for hypothesis H3, including subhypotheses H3.a and H3.b.

5. DISCUSSIONS AND FINDINGS

This study first finds that a cognitively deep state and high levels of environmentalism will eliminate precarious behaviours among CEOs in developing countries, particularly in decision-making related to environmental sustainability. CEOs with a high level of cognitively deep state and environmentalism tend to maintain their commitment to ESG investment and implementation, even when these decisions are not accompanied by adequate organisational bonuses and compensation or incentives. These findings reveal that CEOs' internal orientation toward environmental sustainability is more dominant than their precariat

behaviours, with a stronger long-run orientation (Ostic et al., 2025). The results show that institutional support for ESG investment within organisations is relatively limited. Yet, CEOs in developing countries continue to allocate resources to ESG programs despite sacrificing their compensation (Rau & Yu, 2024). The inner spirits and behavioural consistency reflect the internalisation of deeply rooted cognitive values and environmentalism, enabling CEOs to continue prioritising ESG investments despite potential reductions in their material and psychological well-being (S. Cohen et al., 2023; Gärling & Jansson, 2021). Thus, they have multidimensional behavioural commitments to ESG through cognitive attributions, such as internalisation, long-run orientation, mentality, sustainability, and lower compensation.

Most CEOs in developing countries view ESG investment not merely as an economic decision but as a moral obligation and political responsibility to fulfil international commitments, including the Paris Agreement (von Allwörden, 2025). From a relational agency perspective, findings indicate that CEOs in developing countries are bound by United Nations mandates to promote the implementation of ESG investments (Rau & Yu, 2024; Wang et al., 2024). Their behavioural bonding is reflected in the framework of international governance and jurisprudence (Gao et al., 2023; Hoang et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023). Therefore, this study shows that CEOs in developing countries face low moral hazard risks in avoiding the United Nations ESG mandate, as evidenced by their deep-rooted beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours (Tan et al., 2025). This ethical and moral attachment reduces moral hazard in ESG decision-making because CEOs' beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours align with global sustainability principles (Ostic et al., 2025; Spanò et al., 2025). This study thus confirms that the combination of a cognitively deep state and high environmentalism plays an important role in strengthening CEOs' ESG commitment in developing countries (Saeed & Wiredu, 2025). Thus, the need for simultaneous knowledge contents, a cognitively deep state and environmentalism in constructing individual cognition. Hence, the relationships among each trait of those theories impacts on the constructivism, as intellectual learning developments.

CEOs' beliefs and behaviours in financing ESG investments, especially those related to sustainability issues, are a key factor in reducing precariat behaviours (Ben Ali & Chouaibi, 2023; Hoang et al., 2023; X. Zhang et al., 2020). This study reveals that reductions in precariat behaviour do not occur automatically but rather depend on individuals' levels of knowledge, understanding, and internalisation of ESG investment principles (Ostic et al., 2025). A person with a high level of cognitively deep states has the knowledge capacity to evaluate the long-run consequences of financial decisions, thereby avoiding the short-run orientation that is a key characteristic of low precariat beliefs and behaviours (Spanò et al., 2025; Vu & Nguyen, 2024). This cognitive framework allows individuals to perceive ESG investment not as a burden that reduces material and psychological well-being, but as a behavioural preference of strategic resource allocation that generates sustainable economic, social, and environmental benefits for future generations (Mondéjar-López et al., 2024). Consequently, this study reminds us of the need for precariat behavioural eliminations through knowledge capacity that could be achieved in the long-term perspectives. Even though precariatism relates to the unclear investment yields and returns, education systems should enhance learning capacity for evacuating from intellectual opportunism and adverse moral hazard, such as conducting ESGs' programs and missions

A high level of environmentalism reinforces this study's concept through affective and normative dimensions (L. Xu et al., 2025). Individuals with an environmentalist orientation tend to internalise values of ecological responsibility and social sustainability, thereby consciously discarding a precariat or proletarian mentality focused on individual and short-run interests (Back et al., 2020; S. Cohen et al., 2023; Gärling & Jansson, 2021). The combination of a cognitively deep state and environmentalism creates harmony between human cognition and affection, which in turn encourages CEOs to balance economic interests with social and ecological relations (Rau & Yu, 2024). Thus, ESG financing decisions are not only perceived as instrumental choices but also as practices that reflect ethical responsibility in maintaining sustainable relationships among humans and between humans and natural systems (West et al., 2024). Moreover, this study recommends that the harmonisations of cognitive deep state and environmentalism induce changes in individuals' short- and long-run orientations, ethical and moral obligations, accountability, and responsibility, which constitute obliquely kinetic-active learning systems for individuals.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This study concludes that the combination of a cognitively deep state and high levels of environmentalism plays an important role in suppressing precarious CEO behaviour in developing countries, particularly in

decision-making related to ESG financing and implementation. A cognitively deep state orientation allows CEOs to assess the long-run consequences of sustainable investments, while environmentalism reinforces the affective and normative dimensions that drive ecological and social responsibility. The results of the study show that CEOs' ESG commitments are not solely driven by organisational incentives or institutional support. This commitment is also shaped by the internalisation of deeply rooted sustainability values and adherence to global mandates, such as the Paris Agreement and the United Nations framework. Thus, this study contributes to the understanding that CEOs' psychological factors and internal values are key determinants in strengthening ESG commitment and reducing moral hazard in developing countries. To improve individuals' cognitively deep state and environmentalism, and to eliminate precarious beliefs and behaviours, learning should be based on constructivism within kinetic-active education systems.

This study has limitations, which are described below. First, it designs the experiment based on the negative sides of behaviours captured in a short case. This experiment limits this study's ability to capture the belief and behavioural dynamics underlying CEOs' ESG decisions in real-world contexts and over the long run. Future research opens opportunities to include other adverse behaviours such as self-deficiency syndrome, self-defeating prophecy, paralysis and others. It is also recommended to use longitudinal data or field study methods to examine the consistency of CEOs' ESG beliefs and behaviours over the long term, spanning decades. Second, the study's focus on CEOs in developing countries may limit the generalizability of its findings to developed countries or to different countries' institutional systems, laws, and cultures. Future research can expand the experimental research model by incorporating additional contextual factors, such as political hegemony, regulatory pressure, legal systems, and organisational culture, to gain a more comprehensive understanding of how individuals, mental health characteristics, and institutional factors interact in ESG decision-making.

Appendix A: Questionnaire Items of Two Measured Variables

Cognitively Deep State (Baughn & Yaprak, 1996; Pryke, 2012)

- I am committed to fulfilling my responsibilities as a young individual by promoting a healthy environment.
- I strive to contribute positively to my country by supporting efforts to maintain a healthy environment.
- I recognise my important role in ensuring the well-being of the country's environment.
- I demonstrate respect and care for the environment, believing that protecting nature is a shared responsibility.
- I acknowledge that sustainable investment can serve as a strategic tool to achieve global political supremacy while supporting the objectives of the Paris Agreement.
- I understand that the Paris Agreement requires nations to make sustainable investment decisions to safeguard the environment.
- I recognise that the connection between sustainable investment and global political influence can enhance the implementation and enforcement of the Paris Agreement.

Environmentalism (Herrera, 1992; Schlosberg, 2025)

- I can prevent environmental misuse by implementing proactive measures.
- I can help prevent further disruption to the balance of nature.
- I am committed to addressing critical environmental issues, including pollution, overpopulation, toxic waste, and the depletion of natural resources.
- I contribute to reducing pollution levels that have reached hazardous thresholds.
- I possess the knowledge to implement preventive measures that mitigate environmental pollution risks.
- I can contribute to reducing environmental issues over the next decade.
- I can inspire and influence those around me to take action in preserving the environment.
- I am mindful of my technology usage and can manage its impact on the environment.
- I can identify alternative solutions to address waste storage challenges.
- I actively contribute to conserving natural resources for future generations.
- I am willing to adapt my lifestyle and behaviour to better align with environmental sustainability, fostering a stronger connection between humans and nature.

- I can participate in decision-making processes that directly impact our lives and the environment.
- I play an active role in supporting environmental action groups in tackling various ecological challenges.
- I prioritise environmental protection in my daily actions and decisions.

Appendix B: Protocol for Experiment

This study uses a web-based experimental design to collect data from all CEOs in accounting, finance, operations, or production, as well as from participants in other fields. Completing this material takes approximately 20 to 30 minutes without breaks. At a glance, the display for this study application is in **Figure 2**. The data collection process is as follows:

1. This study began by contacting companies registered in Indonesia via LinkedIn to obtain approval to distribute the research questionnaire. Once permission was obtained, the researchers distributed a link directing respondents to the prepared experimental design website page.
2. Before participants entered their data, the researchers provided detailed explanations of the experimental procedure, including the research stages, the tasks to be performed, and the estimated time required to complete them.
3. After this briefing, we invite participants to access and fill in the required information through the research app at <http://esgprecarity.org/>.
4. When participants entered the experiment website, the system displayed a welcome page that conveyed a message of welcome and confirmed that all data and information collected would be used exclusively for academic research purposes and that confidentiality would be guaranteed. This information was provided to ensure participants understood that their personal data would not be disclosed to any third parties.
5. Next, participants are given a brief, clear explanation of the research objectives, so they have an adequate understanding of the research context and the type of information requested during the completion process.
6. After all information has been provided, participants are asked to express their consent and willingness to participate in the study by selecting the “yes” option to proceed to the next stage and the “no” option if they decide not to participate, which will automatically close the experiment website.
7. Participants are required to fill in general demographic information, including: Email, Full Name, Gender, Age, Occupation, Industry, and Latest Education (Bachelor's, Master's, Doctorate).
8. Participants first complete a questionnaire designed to measure their cognitive depth, assessing their capacity to understand and evaluate the long-term implications of decision-making.
9. Next, participants filled out a questionnaire measuring their level of environmentalism, namely their value orientation and concern for environmental and sustainability issues.
10. After completing the questionnaire, participants were given a decision-making scenario in two conditions: before and after treatment, focusing on precariat beliefs and behaviours. In each case, participants were asked to make decisions related to ESG investment funding and the sustainability of ESG implementation within the organisation.
11. Participants' responses to each case were then evaluated based on their precariat behaviour score, which reflected the extent to which they were willing to fund and voluntarily implement ESG investments.
12. After completing all tasks, participants were prompted to click the “finish” button, which directed them to a closing page with a thank-you message.
13. Then, this app values participants' completed cases and scores before and after treatments. It scored them based on their responses to the provided scenarios. This study takes a golden-rule principle, valuing participants' performance equally. In the higher-bonding, participants who chose the “yes” option were given a score of 100, while those who chose “no” were given a score of 0, both before and after treatment. This procedure was used to capture binary decisions regarding participants' willingness to fund and maintain ESG investments and implementation. Before treatment, when participants selected the “yes” option, the system displayed several value options representing the level of ESG investment funding and ESG implementation sustainability: 400, 380, 350, 320, and

300. Conversely, when participants chose the “no” option, the system displayed lower value options, namely 200, 180, 150, 130, and 100. The participants' final scores were then calculated by dividing the selected value by the maximum value of 400 and converting the result to a percentage. After the treatment, the same procedure is applied with an adjusted range of values. Participants who choose the “yes” option are given the choice of 1000, 980, 950, 920, and 800, while participants who choose the “no” option are given the choice of 700, 680, 650, 630, and 500. The selected scores were then normalised by dividing them by the maximum value of 1000 and converting to percentages. This approach enabled consistent comparison between pre- and post-treatment conditions in subsequent statistical analyses.

14. As a token of appreciation for their participation, the researchers then distributed incentives in accordance with the research provisions.

Figure 2: (A) Designed criteria, (B) Item questions cognitively deep state, (C) Item questions environmentalism, (D) Cases to finance ESG investment and hold ESG, (E) Before treatment beliefs & behaviours, (F) After treatment beliefs & behaviours.

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